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The Causes Of First Military Rule In Pakistan

Aisha Bibi

PhD Scholar at Pakistan Study Centre University of Peshawar
madamaisha17@gmail.com

Dr. Farmanullah

Associate Professor at Pakistan Study Centre University of Peshawar
farman.ullah@uop.edu.pk

Abstract: *There were many causes of the first military rule in Pakistan. No one was sincere to the state after the first Governor-General and prime minister, but every leader wanted to prolong their rule instead of focusing on the country's progress and affairs. They do not want to hold an election to give the masses a chance to elect their representatives. As Pakistan is a democratic country, it needs to hold an election. The first Constitution of Pakistan was framed too late after nine years, but it did not fulfill the people's requirements and was abolished within two years. Besides, every evil was at a peak, such as profiteering, gambling, bribery, and corruption. The politician was playing sea saw to gain the rule. From 1947 to 1958, seven prime ministers changed in undemocratic ways. Ghulam Muhammad, the third Governor-General, dissolved the National Assembly for only their purpose. Every leader uses the Constitution for their purposes. Iskandar Mirza also wanted to prolong his rule; therefore, he was frightened to hold the elections. He feared the people would not elect him again, so he called General Ayub Khan to come and control the situation. He wanted that in this way, he would secure his rule, but after the dissolution of the first assembly, General Ayub Khan resigned him by force and exiled him afterward.*

Keywords: Causes, military rule, inefficient leader, politician, elections, civil administration.

Introduction

The Inefficient leadership caused the first military rule in Pakistan. No one was sincere to the state after independence and the first Governor-General and prime minister. In 1948, after the death of Jinnah, there was no one to fill the vacuum of Jinnah. Liaquat Ali Khan tried hard, but he was assassinated in 1951. The parties were vehicles for personal political advancement. Functionalism was not confined to the Muslim League. Only the opposition party also needed more organizational cohesion. The political parties quarreled with each other on power distribution. "The formation of new political parties in opposition to the Muslim League was against the best interest of Pakistan." Prime Minister Liaquat Ali Khan said, "If the Muslim League is not made powerful and the mushroom growth of the parties is not checked immediately, I am sure that Pakistan, achieved after great sacrifices, will not survive.". In April 1953, Governor General Ghulam Muhammad dissolved the first Constitutional Assembly, and their successor, Muhammad Ali Bogra, an ambassador to the USA, was called and assigned the post of prime minister.

The action of the Governor-General was a big blow to the weak democratic structure in Pakistan and caused a severe political and constitutional crisis. After dissolving the constitution assembly, he said

that it failed to frame a constitution in seven years and had transferred itself to a perpetual body that had lost the confidence of the masses. On average, every ministry lasted for less than 8 months. One of the ministries headed by I.I. Chundrigar remained for only 55 days. His coalition government comprised the Muslim League, the Republican Party, the Kirshak Sarmik Party, and the Nizam-e-Islam Party. Under these circumstances, no government could pay due attention to the problem facing the nation. The Muslim League did not object to the dismissal of its leader.

The National Assembly has played no significant role in the making or unmaking of the cabinet. A vote of no confidence on the floor of the national assembly removed no government. The decision to form a ministry was taken behind closed doors and resulted from the re-alignment of political fiction. The National Assembly merely endorsed it. Everyone wanted to prolong their rule instead of giving special attention to the country's development. In these initial days, Pakistan has faced many problems as framing the constitution, the held election, solving the refugee problems focusing on industrialization, to uphold the life status of the masses but neglecting all the abovementioned problems. The politicians were playing the game of sea saw to gain the rule.

From 1947-1958 seven Prime ministers changed in undemocratic ways. The power of the Governor-General was all in all, and he used this power as he wanted and violated the democratic rules. The third Governor, General Ghulam Muhammad, dissolved the Constitutional Assembly for his purpose. President Iskandar Mirza said in 1957, "It was the foremost duty of every Pakistani to strengthen our armed forces so that the country can live in peace." Still, afterward, he called General Ayub Khan to involve in politics to save his government. But unfortunately, he resigned by force, and after twenty days, he was exiled. Besides this, the politicians were involved to gain the rule, not to progress to the newly created state. These were the reasons that undermined the whole structure of the country. The primary blunder was that the civilians involved the military in politics. However, the responsibility of the Army was to defend the country but not to involve in politics. Besides this, the other problems were delaying of the constitution, lack of proper election, undue interference of the head of the state with ministers and political parties and by the central government with the functioning of the government in the provinces, lack of leadership resulting in the lack of well-organized and disciplined parties, the general lack of character in the politicians and their undue interferences in the administration leads the country to this edge that still we are suffering.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is based on primary and secondary sources ie, books, magazine, library, articles, newspaper, journal, internet to complete the research paper.

Causes of first military rule in Pakistan

There were many causes of military coups and interference in political affairs. Still, overall, the civilian government's central role was giving them a chance to intervene in politics. Its main reasons are as under:

Delaying of the first Constitution

Pakistan came into being in 1947, but its first Constitution was framed after nine years in 1956, while India framed its Constitution within two years. The Constitution is a written document necessary for the country to run its affairs accordingly. The main reason for delaying the Constitution was the inefficiency of political leaders. They were busy to gain the rule and did not give proper attention to the country's development. They were playing sea saw to gain the rule. When the first Constitution was framed in 1956, it was also different from the wishes of the people and political leaders, so it was dismissed after two and a half years.

Dissolution of First Constitution Assembly

Governor-General Ghulam Muhammad dissolved the first Constitution Assembly because the constitution assembly was passing a bill to curtail the power of the Governor-General, so he dismissed the Assembly. The speaker of the Constitutional Assembly challenged this act of the Governor-General in the Sindh Chief Court. Sindh Chief Court gave a verdict in favor of the speaker, but Governor-General appealed to the Federal chief court. A federal court gave a verdict in favor of the Governor-General. This paved the way for the coming Constitution, and the country still suffers. This act of dishonesty created a lack of confidence in the people.

The Interference of Military in Politics

The Army being well organized and disciplined showed its willingness to assist any government determined to maintain law and order. The military's role was in the "non-military" field, giving them the experience to handle civilian problems and expose the incompetency of civil government. With passage of time, the dependency of civilian government on the military increased. The time-limited but continued participation of the military in civilian affairs made the military an essential factor in the decision-making process at the national level and participated in the decline of civilian political institutions.

Delaying of Election

The election is necessary for a democratic state, although elections were promised but never held. Corruption and political bargaining had become the order of the day. In March 1958, Dr. Khan Sahib was assassinated in Lahore. Pakistan was like Hobbs's state of nature, where every political and provincial group fought against any other group. It was a careless and ruthless struggle for power. No political leader wanted to hold an election to prolong their rule as Pakistan is a democratic country and a good form of government. It needs to be held election but never held. The above unpleasant situation creates a hierarchy among the people. The people lost confidence in the country's political leaders and military control affairs.

Economic Crisis

The economic crisis was at a high peak; Pakistan had a severe economic crisis in 1958. The scarcity of consumer goods, the rising prices, the shortage of food, large-scale deficit financing by the government and financial indiscipline were all the unmistakable indications of a declining economy. The government treasury was empty, and foreign exchange reserves were down to about Rs. 240 million, of which about Rs. 140 million were not negotiable. The country incurs a foreign exchange liability of Rs. 30 million monthly. Besides this, uncertain weather conditions and crop failures played their part; the main reason was the widespread political confusion in the country. There was widespread industrial unrest, and strikes became common. But no government could give serious thought to the economy and evolve practical and lasting solutions to the economic problem of Pakistan.

Need to Change condition.

The people became hopeless from the worst situation created by the politician. There was a general feeling amongst the educated people perturbed by the degeneration of politics. The people need to find a chance to the possibility of the politician changing or reforming their methods. The only way of the turmoil was the replacement of a parliamentary system of government, which could ensure the country's political stability and economic development. The people have started looking towards the Army to provide strong leadership.

Developmental planning

Developmental planning during 1947-58 was disrupted due to political instability and hampered the systematic implementation of development plans, and their efforts could not yield satisfactory results. Although a six-year development board prepared in 1951-57 and five years of planning were also formulated, it finally failed to achieve most of its objective. The main reason for its failure was the politician was busy in their tussle to gain the rule. They should have given more attention to the developmental plan of the country. This gives a chance for Army to intervene in politics and country the country's situation.

Sino-Indian Conflict

The severe other reason was the Sino-Indian conflict, which severely ramifications South Asian regional politics and especially Indo-Pakistan relations. For the first time, India was face to face with a more significant military power, a situation like that of Pakistan vis-a-vis India after the first Kashmir war in 1948-49. Pakistan urged and sought the assistance of the Army for their issues. The Army started an interest in political affairs. At last, they were fully involved in politics instead of defending the country. But the role played by the civilian to involve the military in politics. This paved the way for the military in the future, with which we are still suffering.

Administrative Vacuums

Like Pakistan, a developing country expected the state that practically dictates ad-hoc decision-making is paid no heed. At last, the voter respondent solely to the brave, selfless king who occasionally descends from their thrones to provide instant gratification, only to a speedy return to their abodes. Such types of administration vacuums exist in Pakistan. Where everyone is left at the mercy of the nefarious forces, all types of disaster man made or natural, show the inadequacies within our civilian setup quite frequently, and we keep depending on the excellent work done by the military in times of emergencies.

Lack of Sincere leaders

Due to a lack of sincere leaders, Army never took over the country's power to it and controlled leadership only to protect people from misrule and tyranny. But the military claimed that they seized power not for their own sake but because somebody had to rescue the country from abuse of state powers.

Unsatisfactory Role of Muslim League

The creation of the Pakistan Muslim League did not play its due role in developing the newly created country, and it lost its prestige because of a group of opportunists. No political leader was sincere and serious about nation-building. Resultantly, political history reveals that maximum politicians prefer personal interests to national ones. The country remains in the grip of lands lords, Nawabs, Chaudhries, and Sardars who never care for the development and progress of the country. Thus consequently, unrest among the masses paved the way for army rule.

Ineffective legislature

Legislative bodies have also shown no sincerity as it is a supreme body and making policies for the betterment of the country. But it failed for these reasons, to promote the voting system, lack of qualification for the legislature, lack of consciousness, monopoly of self-seeking and political bargaining, lota crazy and floor crossing and irresponsible attitude of political parties. The legislative body needed to provide effective laws and satisfy people's basic facilities and justice. Due to the unpleasant situation above, people were disappointed in political leaders and wanted rapid change to be impossible without a military coup.

Corrupt bureaucracy

Corruption and defunct civil administrator setup were responsible for the decline of Pakistan. Bureaucracy can work for the welfare of the public desired. But the situation produced and developed corruption at all levels. The civil servant of Pakistan was responsible for destroying national resources and wealth with bear hands. The abovementioned situation reached a severe level that the government imposed the "Prevention of Corruption Rules 1953" to check bureaucracy. But it not in implemented as all politicians were the friend of same days. The above reasons were a clear road map for Army to control the worst situation in the country.

Undemocratic Attitudes of politicians

Democracy is the best form of government as Pakistan became a democratic country, but democratic culture was not produced as needed. It has specific prerequisites, such as influential political parties, good leadership, democratic culture and tolerance. Political leaders and political parties are the spirits of democracy. However, political leaders and parties still need to provide a political environment. Therefore, the military interfered in the politics and affairs of the country.

National Problems

Democratic government is beneficial to solve the nation's problems but not to multiply the fire. But in Pakistan, the situation was radically changed; corruption, inflation, unemployment, deteriorated law and order and injustice in the society was at the high peek; these evils created hatred in the heart of the masses against the political leaders. The following situations create an atmosphere for the Army to coup.

Political Instability

Political instability was in the high peek. Every leader was given preference to their interest instead of national interest. This decline of civilians resulted from a severe political leadership crisis within a couple of years of independence. The history of Pakistan is very hurtful from 1951-58, it had only two Governor-General and one commander-in-chief while seven prime ministers toppled after one another. They were playing the game of the sea and saw for the rule. Besides this, a substantial nexus was created between civil bureaucracy and the military. Its result appeared that civilians failed to control the country's worst situation, which involved a military coup and control the country.

The Role of the Judiciary

The judiciary has a significant role in proclaiming social justice, law and order in the country but in Pakistan; the situation was different. A democratic constitution means providing a list of fundamental rights of the people recognized and guaranteed by the independent judiciary. The judiciary is not only the guardian of the Constitution but also the safeguard of the people's fundamental rights and their role is arbitrary in the country. But in Pakistan, the judiciary did not play its due role and became subservient to the executive. In 1955, the federal court's decision had far-reaching repercussions; it implied that all the acts passed by the Constitutional Assembly in its constituent capacity were invalid because none of them had received the permission of the Governor-General. The federal court thereby ruled that the Governor-General's assent was necessary for all legislation passed by the central legislature. Notwithstanding the dynamics of democracy, chief justice Munir upheld the governor general's decision on technical grounds and paved the first military rule and General Ayub Khan. The higher judiciary shares the burden of military rule in Pakistan. This opened the door for Army and civil political adventure in Pakistan.

Lack of independent election commission

The lack of an independent election commission was also a significant cause of military rule in Pakistan. Pakistan did not hold a democratic election for about eleven years after independence, and democratic values had scarcely struck roots. An independent and powerful election commission was the guarantor of free and fair elections and multi-party based permanent of Pakistani politics. The election commission remained always under the control of politicians, especially of the ruling party. It had never played a democratic role as it needed. The electoral politics in Pakistan led to the continuous narrowing and increasing unrepresentativeness and unresponsiveness of the self-perpetuating political elite that so irretrievably discredited the parliamentary structure and process that it got brushed aside by the military elite by a decade after its birth.

International Threats

From the initial stage, Pakistan threatened India and other superior countries. India never accepted Pakistan, and in the very early stage, it created many more problems that it never re-control and rehabilitated itself. India was also a big hurdle from the west side as Bengal was its main center of their heed. They did not want the stable situation of the western part of Pakistan. Due to the abovementioned problems, Pakistan joined SENTO and SEATO Pacts; the Pakistan army was the center of the pacts. For the United States, it was easy to deal with military leadership than the political elite. America extended her tacit support to the military intervention into politics in Pakistan in the 1950s. International politics was a significant threat to military intervention in Pakistani politics. The Pakistan army was the center of this move. It was effortless for the United States to deal with army leadership instead of the political elite.

The United States extended her support to Pakistan's army intervention in politics, while Pakistan has vis-a-vis concern for her security from the Indian invasion. During the Cold War, international politics was a significant factor in the military interference in the politics of Pakistan. The result of American patronage of Pakistan's military rulers contributed to the inability of democracy to take root in the country.

The declaration of martial law

When the abovementioned situation accorded, and the condition was out of control, General Yahya Khan ordered General Ayub Khan to proclaim martial law to control the situation. Yahya Khan aimed to secure his rule, but Ayub Khan exiled and resigned him by force after 20 days. After the death of the deputy speaker of the East Pakistan assembly in September 1958, the military finally decided to displace the civil government. The C-in-C asked the chief of army staff to prepare a plan for the take-over of the civil administration. The military take-over and declaration of martial law was proclaimed on 7th October 1958. President Iskandar Mirza abrogated the Constitution and dissolved provincial and national assemblies. Political parties were banned, General Ayub Khan was appointed supreme commander of the armed force, and martial and was declared throughout the county. President Iskandar Mirza explained the pathetic condition and the growing corruption in the society and the inability of the politicians to change their ways and lift him with no alternative but to take this step. The statement of present Iskandar Mirza disclosed that civilians give a chance to the military to coup and interfere in government.

Conclusion

There were many causes of military rule in Pakistan. The political machinery in Pakistan degenerated rapidly after the demise of Jinnah and Liaquat Ali Khan. Pakistan needed more clear and competent leadership and well-organized political parties to aggregate the interest in the national political framework. On the other military was gaining strength, and the worst political situation shifted the real political power of the military. The role of the Army in politics gave them experience in handling

civilian problems and exposed the incompetence of the civil government.

The limited but continued participation of the Army in civilian affairs made the Army play crucial actors in the decision-making process at the national level. It precipitated the decline of the civilian political institution. The history of Pakistan is full of insincere leaders who only wanted to prolong their rule instead of focusing on the country's problems. The failure of civilian government is the leading cause of military-political intervention. Although Pakistan is a democratic country, the politician did not give any attention to their solidarity, stability and integrity but preferred their interest instead of the national interest. The intervention of the Pakistani Army into politics is the reason for civilian political leaders. The military's role is to defend the country, not interfere in politics. Military intervention in politics has always been related to major social, political, economic, and educational factors. Pakistan inherited well-established supremacy of civil-political over army institutions under the British government. However, Pakistan degenerated into a praetorian state with dreadful politics and economic and social fallouts. Military interference in politics is the transformation of various variables such as failure of civilians, inefficient leadership, natural disasters, election and Constitution delays, and lack of sincere leadership and social-economic factors. There were always deficiencies within our governance systems that prompted debugging exercises from the most powerful institutions in Pakistan. But the other factors of a military coup in politics were lack of transparency, accountability, and lack of responsibility in democratic governance could go a long way in stabilizing the country to the control of the Army. The assertion at the time of military take-over that they would return the country to civilian rule as soon as possible does not imply that they will abandon interest in politics. The limited but continued participation of the military in civilian affairs made the military an essential factor in the decision-making process at the national level and participated in the decline of civilian political institutions. Once the armed forces entered politics, it became difficult for them to disassociate themselves from politics.

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